

EDAP+ TN on Quality Assessment of SPIRE GNSS-R L2 Ocean

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

SPIRE Global is a data and Analytics Company that designs, builds, tests, operates and collects data from its satellite constellation composed of Lemur-2 satellites. Each of these satellites carry two payloads: STRATOS GPS radio occultation meteorology payload and SENSE AIS payload for ship tracking.

STRATOS is the SPIRE GNSS receiver for remote sensing & precision orbit determination and is able to perform multiple tasking:

- Precise Orbit Determination using the zenith L1, L2 antenna;
- Performs radio occultation on high-gain, side-mounted L1, L2 antennas;
- enables atmospheric & ionospheric remote sensing;
- modified STRATOS are used for passive bistatic radar (GNSS-R) applications.

This document is the assessment of the Level 2 Ocean Wind Speed and mean square slope (mss) product. The measurement technique is GNSS Reflectometry (GNSS-R) that involves making measurements of the reflections from the Earth using navigation signals from the Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS). The GNSS-R measures the phase delay of the reflected signal given by the interaction with ocean surface to infer the ocean roughness and associate to it the surface wind speed and mss.

During the compilation of this study a new version of the ocean products have been developed by SPIRE team and they provide us an updated dataset and user manuals. Because the assessment of the first version at the time of the delivery of this new information was almost completed, we decided to include in the study both versions, named here V1 and V2. Measurements are collected by Batch-1 FM109 and FM110 satellites for V1 and by Batch-1 satellite FM109 and Batch-2 satellites (FM 146 and FM147) for V2.

SPIRE data are generally documented, with the description of all the variables presents in the files and the presence of numerous metadata even if some information should be explicated more clearly. L1 documentation deeply characterizes the sensor, the calibration, and the geometrical aspect of the measurements; the delivered L2 Product Manual basically describes the retrieval algorithm. Wind speed is correlated with its uncertainty, in form of standard deviation of the statistical procedure used in the retrieval, while mss uncertainty is not present.

SPIRE wind speed data have been intercompared with three different references, two satellites and a ground reference. The first satellite reference is CYclone Global Navigation Satellite System (CYGNSS, RD-5), employing a GNSS-R measurement technique and the second one is Advanced SCATterometer (ASCAT, RD-7), an instrument on board of Meteorological operational satellite – B (MetOp-B). The ground reference chosen is the TAO/TRITON buoys array (RD-6), designed for the study of year-to-year climate variations related to El Niño and the Southern Oscillation.

SPIRE mss data have been intercompared with CYGNSS data (CYGNSS Level 2 Science Data Record, Version 3.1). CYGNSS mss retrieval is directly cited as reference in the user guide for this product, so it can be considered a natural choice for the intercomparison exercise.

The intercomparison has been carried on the equatorial region between [-8, 8] deg latitude and [-135, -90] deg longitude for both wind speed and mss. The co-location criteria used for the intercomparison are 0.23 deg maximum latitude/longitude distance (about 25 km)

and 15, 60 and 5 minutes of maximum temporal distance for CYGNSS, ASCAT and TAO respectively for wind speed and 0.23 deg maximum latitude/longitude distance and 15 minutes for mss.

The V1 wind speed intercomparison results are similar for the three references, although a less number co-located couples SPIRE-TAO have been identified. SPIRE uncertainty is generally higher with respect to the references. Results reveal a good agreement between SPIRE and the references, with correlation coefficients of 0.81, 0.77 and 0.73 for CYGNSS, ASCAT and TAO respectively. For wind lower than 8 m/s the single differences are not significative (within the combined uncertainty). However, a negative bias emerges, gaining importance with the increase of the wind speed. For measurement of 10 m/s of the references a mean bias of about -2 m/s is revealed, that keep growing for even stronger winds and leading to an underestimation of the energetic phenomena like tornadoes and hurricanes.

V2 wind speed intercomparison produces similar results of V1; for this version we found a greater number of coincidences with ASCAT, so we decided to employ a temporal threshold of 15 minutes for coincidences even for this satellite. The correlation coefficients found are 0.80, 0.80 and 0.74 for CYGNSS, ASCAT and TAO respectively. V2 bias as function of reference wind speed has the same behaviour of V1 but is positive shifted. This positive offset mitigates the bias affecting strong winds but could introduce a positive offset for lower winds.

The mss intercomparison is based on CYGNSS uncertainty; SPIRE mss uncertainty is not provided and has been considered equal to zero. The two instruments reveal similar features in the spatial map and a similar trend in the temporal analysis. A strong bias has been revealed (mean value -0.0061, becoming more dominant for higher mss value) and a correlation of 0.56, with the larger part of SPIRE dataset not within reference uncertainty. No particular difference has been found between V1 and V2.

In order to understand the reason of the mss bias a comparison between the normalized bistatic radar cross section (nbrcs) given with SPIRE and CYGNSS mss products has been carried on. The results reveal a good correlation between the two values but a strong bias that could be originated from the different calibration methods.

1.1 References

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

RD-1. EDAP Best Practice Guidelines, EDAP.REP.001, v2.1, 31st October 2021.

RD-2. Earth Observation Mission Quality Assessment Framework ...

RD-3. SPIRE GNSS-R Level 2 Ocean Product Manual, v1.2, 1st July 2022.

RD-4. SPIRE Near-Nadir GNSS-R Level 1 Product Manual, v1.2, 1st May 2022.

RD-5. CYGNSS Handbook, v1.0, 1st April 2016.

RD-6. TAO-TRITON buoys array website:
https://tao.ndbc.noaa.gov/proj_overview/proj_overview_ndbc.shtml

RD-7. ASCAT Wind Product User Manual, v1.17, 1st December 2021.

RD-8. ASCAT wind validation report, v1.0, 16th May 2018.

RD-9. SMAP documentation: <https://smap.jpl.nasa.gov/documents/>

RD-10. Al-Khaldi, M. M., Gleason, S., Linnabary, R., & Policelli, F. S. (2023). Level-1 Calibration Assessment of Spire's LEMUR-2 GNSS-R Ocean Normalized Bistatic Radar Cross Section Estimates. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, 20, 1-5.

RD-11. Spire Level 2 Ocean Wind Derived from GNSS-R Bistatic Radar Product Summary V1.1, 1st March 2023

RD-12. ECMWF ocean surface wind field description: [ECMWF | Parameter details](#)

RD-13. SPIRE GNSS-R Level 2 Ocean Product Manual, v1.3, 1st March 2023. Updated product manual delivered during the assessment for Version 2.

RD-14. SPIRE Near-Nadir GNSS-R Level 1 Product Manual, v1.3, 1st March 2023. Updated L1 manual delivered during the assessment for Version 2.

1.2 Glossary

ASCAT: Advanced SCATterometer

CYGNSS: CYclone Global Navigation Satellite System

GNSS: Global Navigation Satellite Systems

GNSS-R: Global Navigation Satellite Systems Reflectometry

ECMWF: European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts

MetOp-B: Meteorological operational satellite – B

MSS: ocean surface Mean Square Slope

SMAP: Soil Moisture Active Passive

V1: Spire GNSS-R Level 2 Ocean Product Manual - v1.2, first version of dataset delivered for the intercomparison

V2: Spire GNSS-R Level 2 Ocean Product Manual - v1.3, second version of dataset delivered for the intercomparison

1.3 Cal/Val Maturity Matrices

1.3.1 Data Versions differences

As explained in the Executive Summary two versions of SPIRE L2 Ocean products have been analysed. V1 only used Batch-1 GNSS-R satellites, FM109 and FM110, but the version 2 enabled ocean observations on the Batch-2 GNSS-R satellites, FM146 and FM147. Also, one of the Batch-1 satellites (FM110) suffered an early failure of its zenith antenna that affected the calibration; version 1 dataset employed this satellite to perform

ocean wind-speed retrieval, but in V2 FM110 has been disabled given the alternative data from Batch-2. Therefore, the V2 enables FM146 and FM147, but disables FM110.

On the documentation/algorithm side, V2 is very similar to V1, with the addition of a better characterisation and screening of L1 data adding new variable flags. V2 L2 data files have the same variables and flags of the V1. For this reason, the Data Provider Documentation Review Maturity Matrix will be the same for both versions.

In the intercomparison the two versions have been analysed separately, but the Validation Grades proposed are the same for both, so they share the same Maturity Matrix.

1.3.2 Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix Ocean

Data Provider Documentation Review			Validation Summary	Key
Product Information	Metrology	Product Generation		Not Assessed
Product Details	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	Measurement Validation Method	Not Assessable	
Availability & Accessibility	Measurement Validation Results Compliance	Basic		
Product Format, Flags & Metadata	Metrological Traceability Documentation	Geometric Validation Method	Good	
User Documentation	Geometric Validation Results Compliance	Excellent		
	Ancillary Data			Ideal
				Not Public

Figure 1.3.2.1: Summary Matrix Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

1.3.3 Wind speed validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

SPIRE wind speed detailed validation				Key
Measurement		Geometric		
SPIRE vs CYGNSS Method	SPIRE vs CYGNSS Results Compliance	SPIRE vs CYGNSS Method	SPIRE vs CYGNSS Results Compliance	Not Assessed
SPIRE vs ASCAT Method	SPIRE vs ASCAT Results Compliance	SPIRE vs ASCAT Method	SPIRE vs ASCAT Results Compliance	Not Assessable
SPIRE vs TAO Method	SPIRE vs TAO Results Compliance	SPIRE vs TAO Method	SPIRE vs TAO Results Compliance	Basic
				Good
				Excellent
				Ideal
				🔒 Not Public

Figure 1.3.3.1: Wind speed Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

1.3.4 MSS Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

SPIRE mss detailed validation				Key
Measurement		Geometric		
SPIRE vs CYGNSS Method	SPIRE vs CYGNSS Results Compliance	SPIRE vs CYGNSS Method	SPIRE vs CYGNSS Results Compliance	Not Assessed
				Not Assessable
				Basic
				Good
				Excellent
				Ideal
				🔒 Not Public

Figure 1.3.4.1: mss Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

1.3.5 Normalized bistatic radar cross section (nbrcs) Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

SPIRE nbrcs detailed validation				Key
Measurement		Geometric		
SPIRE vs CYGNSS Method	SPIRE vs CYGNSS Results Compliance	SPIRE vs CYGNSS Method	SPIRE vs CYGNSS Results Compliance	Not Assessed
				Not Assessable
				Basic
				Good
				Excellent
				Ideal
				🔒 Not Public

Figure 1.3.5.1: nbrcs Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

2. DATA PROVIDER DOCUMENTATION REVIEW

2.1 Product Information

Product Details	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Data are generally well documented, even if some information misses or is not explicitly reported in the provided documentation.
Product Name	SPIRE GNSS-R L2 Ocean
Sensor Name	STRATOS (GNSS-R) The satellite id number which makes the measurement is present in the metadata "rx_id". Transmitter name is present in the file name. The antennas used present in global attribute "antennas" and in variables. GNSS-R satellites have measure with two different antennas.
Sensor Type	GNSS-R
Mission Type	SPIRE is a constellation of more than 100 satellites, although the Ocean product is measured by four satellites.
Mission Orbit	37 degrees inclination - 4 Satellites (FM109, FM110, FM146, FM147)
Product Version Number	v2.1 (version 1), v2.2 (version 2)
Product ID	Not clearly reported
Processing level of product	Level 2
Measured Quantity Name	Wind, ocean surface mean square slope (mss), nbrcs (normalized bistatic radar cross section, reported from L1 data).
Measured Quantity Units	m s ⁻¹ , dimensionless, dB (dimensionless).
Stated Measurement Quality	Not a direct quality grade assigned to the measurement.
Spatial Resolution	L1 data present the variable "eff_area_at_sp", effective area at specular point. This variable is the effective area of the ocean that is averaged to obtain the normalized bistatic radar cross section (nbrcs) employed in the retrieval of wind speed and mss. It can be considered a measurement of spatial resolution, but it is not present in L2 data, even if the files report the L1 file used for the retrieval. Examining L1 data the effective area of the provided dataset is within 83 and 681 km ² with a mean value of 245 km ² and a standard deviation of 110 km ² . These values correspond to a square with side within [9, 26] km, minimum/maximum values, with a mean side of 16 km and a standard deviation of 10 km. Additionally, even if the horizontal resolution of the products is not explicitly reported, [RD-3] refers to an along track 5-point median filter and 5-point boxcar filter to the variables used in nbrcs calculation due to the need of noise suppression. Citing [RD-3]: "Calibration signals and direct power are smoothed with the larger sliding filter during L1 processing. This results in an along-track signal smoothing of about 35 km"; this process leads to an increase of horizontal resolution along track (minimum 35 km).

Spatial Coverage	Global coverage, sea.
Temporal Resolution	Revisit time not clearly reported.
Temporal Coverage	Not present in the metadata. Information not clearly present in RD-3
Point of Contact	Not present in the metadata. Information not clearly present in RD-3
Product locator (DOI/URL)	Not present in the metadata. Information not clearly present in RD-3
Conditions for access and use	Commercial Data, conditions defined by contract
Limitations on public access	Not present in the metadata. Information not clearly present in RD-3
Product Abstract	GNSS Reflectometry (GNSS-R) involves making measurements of the reflections from the Earth using navigation signals from the Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS). Using GNSS-R reflections from the ocean, this product derive the sea surface roughness and near surface wind from the measured intensity of the reflected signal.

Availability & Accessibility		
Grade: Good		
Justification	The proposed grade is good: products are compliant to some FAIR principles, but no Data Management Plan is provided, and no data catalogue published. This score could be increased providing them.	
Compliant with FAIR principles	Partially compliant	
	To be Findable:	
	F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	Yes, the file name is generated univocally
	F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)	yes
	F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes	No
	F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	No
	To be Accessible:	
	A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol	No
	A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	No
A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary	No	

	A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	No
	To be Interoperable:	
	I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	Yes
	I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	Yes
	I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	Yes, the file L1B that generates the data
	To be Reusable:	
	R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	Partially, some important information still lacks. In particular I suggest adding spatial and temporal resolution and coverage, see the previous paragraph.
	R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	Yes, but not explicitly reported in the file itself
	R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	Yes
	R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	Yes
Data Management Plan	Not available to the users.	
Availability Status	There is no product catalogue publicly available online. Data availability defined by contract.	

Product Format, Flags & Metadata	
Grade: Good	
Justification	It does not appear that data provider follows a standard convention for metadata. However, they are enough self-explaining. Product Format is described in [RD-11] and publicly available.
Product File Format	<i>netCDF4</i>
Metadata Conventions	<i>Metadata not clearly follows a specific convention</i>
Analysis Ready Data?	No

User Documentation		
Grade: Good		
Justification	The user provides a PUG that explains basically how the product is derived and the retrieval algorithm, referring also to RD-5 for further details. However, the documentation lacks a clear explanation of the uncertainty computation and its sources. For V2 documentation I suggest providing FM146 and FM147 calibration curves.	
<i>Document</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>QA4ECV Compliant</i>
Product User Guide	GNSS-R Level 2 Ocean Product Manuals [RD-3], [RD-13]	No
ATBD	GNSS-R Level 2 Ocean Product Manuals [RD-3], [RD-13], with reference at CYGNSS Handbook (April 2016)	No

2.2 Metrology

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	The calibration chain and equations are described in RD-4 with an example of calibration relative power between front-end. In ground testing, The calibration system was shown to meet the requirement of power ratio measurement calibration better than +/- 0.25 dB. Additionally, all the key components of the instrumentation are described (e.g., antenna gains).
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Spire Near-Nadir GNSS-R Level 1 Product Manual</i>

Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Antenna gains and sensibilities with respect to signal directions are documented in [RD-4] and considered fit for purpose.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Spire Near-Nadir GNSS-R Level 1 Product Manuals RD-4, RD-14</i>

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Traceability chain briefly described in User Manual, uncertainty diagram not present in the provided documentation.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>GNSS-R Level 2 Ocean Product Manuals [RD-3], [RD-13]</i>

Uncertainty Characterisation	
Grade: Basic	
Justification	<p>Wind is retrieved with a statistical inference approach; uncertainty values is provided as standard deviation of wind measurements, but no uncertainty components analysis provided.</p> <p>The mss uncertainty is not provided in the product files. The Product Manual [RD-3] cites [RD-5] for mss retrieval, but does not give any direct reference to the uncertainty, so it will considered as not present.</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>GNSS-R Level 2 Ocean Product Manuals RD-3, RD-13</i> • <i>CYGNSS Handbook RD-5</i>

Ancillary Data	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>ECMWF gridded analysis with $\frac{1}{8}$ degree resolution is used to obtain the “truth” wind speed collocated with the GNSS-R observations. The background near-surface wind is derived from 10U and 10V variables of the standard ECMWF GRIB files. The Background Wind is stored in NetCDF files with the same structure as the Level 2 gbrOcn ocean files.</p> <p>Salinity map 2020 SMAP is employed to calculate sea water dielectric constant, used in turn to obtain Fresnel reflection coefficient. A simple salinity calculation function is obtained by averaging 12 months and all longitudes. Missing data are replaced with values averaged over higher than 50 degrees latitude, both north and south.</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>GNSS-R Level 2 Ocean Product Manuals RD-3, RD-13</i> • https://apps.ecmwf.int/codes/grib/param-db/?id=166 • https://salinity.oceansciences.org/smap-salinity.htm

2.3 Product Generation

Calibration Algorithm	
Grade: Good	
Justification	The signal injection approach couples a calibration signal into each of the front-ends. This approach is commonly used for the calibration of phased array antennas and allows measurement of phase as well as amplitude. Data from land and ocean are processed with different chains. Signal and calibration quantities reported in L1 files.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Spire Near-Nadir GNSS-R Level 1 Product Manual</i>

Geometric Processing	
Grade: Good	
Justification	The Geometric Processing is described in detail in the RD-4. Geometric information is detailly documented in the L1 files.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Spire Near-Nadir GNSS-R Level 1 Product Manuals RD-4, RD-14</i>

Retrieval Algorithm	
Grade: Good	
Justification	The retrieval process is documented in [RD-3], with reference to the CYGNSS algorithm [RD-5]. The algorithm employed is very similar to those used by CYGNSS, so can be considered fit for purpose for a GNSS-R wind measurement. However, the Good grade is not fully achieved due to the lack of a sensitivity study and a bias analysis. The data provider proposes these investigations for a future development.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Spire GNSS-R Level 2 Ocean Product Manuals RD-3, RD-13</i>

Mission-Specific Processing	
Grade: Not Assessable	
<i>Additional Processing</i>	
Justification	No Additional Processing documented for the product.
Reference	<i>Spire GNSS-R Level 2 Ocean Product Manuals RD-3, RD-13</i>

3. DETAILED VALIDATION – MEASUREMENT

3.1 Introduction

In order to better understand the potentiality of SPIRE mission, three months of data have been requested to the data provider on a region on west of the South America coast. The region selected for the intercomparison exercise is comprised between [8, -8] deg latitude and [-90, -135] deg longitude (Figure 1.3.5.1), and the time period chosen is from 1st June 2021 to 31st August 2021. This particular region has been selected due the presence of the TAO/TRITON array of buoys [RD-6] floating in the ocean, measuring several parameters, included the surface wind intensity. The provided data have been measured by four satellites of the SPIRE constellation, characterized by numbers FM109, FM110, FM146 and FM147.

SPIRE datasets contains two products: the ocean surface wind speed and the mean square slope of the ocean surface (mss). The first is the measure of the wind intensity, calculated using L1 normalized bistatic radar cross section with a calibration curve; this curve has been obtained from a statistical comparison from L1 measurements and the wind speed at 10 m above the surface from ECMWF. The mss is defined as the variance in the sea surface slope; this quantity can be estimated from the following equation as described in the RD-3 and RD-5.

$$mss = \frac{|R(\theta)|^2}{\sigma_0}$$

Where $R(\theta)$ is the complex Fresnel coefficient estimated at the specular point and σ_0 the normalized bistatic radar cross section. The Fresnel coefficient is calculated using as ancillary data, the sea water dielectric constant, depending from water temperature and salinity and provided by SMAP data [RD-9].

Figure 1.3.5.1: region selected for the intercomparison (marked by orange box), and position of the TAO/TRITON buoys used as ground reference (yellow diamonds).

SPIRE wind speed data have been intercompared with three different reference datasets, two from satellite instruments and one from ground stations. The ground reference selected is the TAO array of buoys cited above, while the selected satellites are CYGNSS [RD-5] and ASCAT on METOP-B [RD-7].

SPIRE mss data have been intercompared with CYGNSS dataset. CYGNSS is cited in [RD-3] as reference for the mss retrieval and is a natural candidate for the intercomparison. SPIRE does not provide an uncertainty value for mss, so the uncertainty in the intercomparison calculation will be treated as equal to 0. CYGNSS product used in the intercomparison is CYGNSS Level 2 Science Data Record, Version 3.1.

CYGNSS is a NASA Earth Venture mission, managed by the Earth System Science Pathfinder Program. The mission consists of a constellation of eight small satellites. The eight observatories comprise a constellation that measures the ocean surface wind field with very high temporal resolution and spatial coverage, under all precipitating conditions, and over the full dynamic range of wind speeds experienced in a tropical cyclone. The CYGNSS observatories fly in 510 km circular orbits at a common inclination of 35, 302 and 260 deg. Each observatory includes a Delay Doppler Mapping Instrument (DDMI) consisting of a modified GPS receiver capable of measuring surface scattering, a low gain zenith antenna for measurement of the direct GPS signal, and two high gain nadir antennas for measurement of the weaker scattered signal. Each DDMI is capable of measuring 4 simultaneous bi-static reflections, resulting in a total of 32 wind measurements per second by the full constellation. This dataset provides ocean surface wind speeds produced by a processing algorithm and geophysical model function to convert the bistatic radar cross section to wind speed.

Each CYGNSS wind observation covers an area of 25x25 km. CYGNSS wind retrieval is cited in SPIRE documentation as the theoretical model on which SPIRE wind retrieval has been developed; this lead CYGNSS to be a natural choice for a reference dataset in an intercomparison exercise and is also used in literature as reference for the intercomparison exercises [RD-10] between the missions.

The second instrument employed as reference is the Advanced SCATterometer (ASCAT) [RD-7] on board on Meteorological Operational B (MetOp-B). MetOp-B is an European Space Agency (ESA) mission and is operated by the European organisation for the exploitation of METeorological SATellite (EUMETSAT). MetOp-B was launched on 17 September 2012 and still in operation. ASCAT is a real aperture radar using vertically polarised antennas. It transmits a long pulse with Linear Frequency Modulation; ground echoes are received by the instrument, and the backscattered signal is spectrally analysed and detected. The instrument operates at a frequency of 5.255 GHz (C-band), which allow to operate even in rain condition.

Although ASCAT retrieval is based on fit procedures similar to those described in the other two satellites documentations, it employs a different kind of instrument (radar) and offers the possibility to have an independent measurement technique with respect to SPIRE and CYGNSS. For the intercomparison we employed ASCAT ocean surface wind measurements, given with a 25 km grid. Another ocean wind product is available with a 12.5 km resolution, but it is specifically dedicated to coastal area and SPIRE measurements are given with a minimum distance of 50 km from the coasts, as reported in [RD-3].

ASCAT files do not directly report the uncertainty on wind speed measurements. An estimation of product measurements accuracy and precision can be found on [RD-8]. This document compares ASCAT measurements with ECMWF forecast for ocean surface wind. For the 25 km resolution product the document reports a negligible mean bias with respect to ECMWF measurements and a mean dispersion of 1.13 m/s (Figure 2 of [RD-8]). This value has been employed as uncertainty on ASCAT measurements.

The study will often present the difference between measurements, together with the difference uncertainty: the difference uncertainty will be always calculated as the squared sum of the two independent uncertainties. In the comparison also, a difference will be defined significative when the absolute value of the ratio between difference and difference uncertainty will be larger than 1.

3.2 SPIRE ocean surface wind intercomparison

The following paragraph describes the ocean surface wind speed product intercomparison.

3.2.1 Measurements screening

All measurements used have been screened according to the quality flags and criteria reported in their respective documentation.

SPIRE measurements have been screened according to the variables *quality_flag* and *wind_confidence*. SPIRE screening process result in 120 discarded data on a total of 129004, about 0.1% for V1 and 299 discarded data on a total of 125441, about 0.24% for V2. Discarded data are concentrated in the high wind region (above 8 m/s).

CYGNSS measurements have been screened eliminating the data marked as *poor quality* by the variable *sample_flag* (values 1, 64 and 128) and requesting the wind speed measured to be inside of wind speed validity range, given as an attribute value of the variable *wind_speed*. ASCAT measurements have been screened according to the quality flag variable *wvc_quality_flag* rejecting measurements that do not pass the product monitoring checks as suggested in [RD-7].

3.2.2 Satellites datasets general overview

For the first step of the intercomparison, a general observation of the three datasets has been carried on. Figure 3.2.2.1 and Figure 3.2.2.2 show respectively the histograms of the absolute and relative number of occurrences of a certain value of the wind speed in the two datasets (bin width equal to 1 m/s).

Figure 3.2.2.1: histogram of number of measurements vs wind speed value in SPIRE CYGNSS and ASCAT datasets.

Figure 3.2.2.2 highlights a difference in the relative occurrence of measurements of stronger winds (above 8 m/s) between SPIRE V1 and the two references. While CYGNSS and ASCAT show a similar data distribution, SPIRE V1 distribution is left-shifted, suggesting a bias affecting higher winds. This effect is reduced in V2 that presents just a difference in the tail thickness of the distribution. The presence of a bias is reported in [RD-3] and [RD-13] and will be studied in future developments of the retrieval algorithm.

This bias for the stronger wind is also confirmed by Figure 3.2.2.3, Figure 3.2.2.4, Figure 3.2.2.5 and Figure 3.2.2.6 in which wind speed local averages, calculated during the intercomparison period are mapped (bins width equal to 2.5 deg longitude and 1 deg

latitude) for SPIRE, CYGNSS and ASCAT respectively. As can be seen, while ASCAT and CYGNSS maps show similar behaviours, SPIRE underestimates the average values on the southern region with respect of the two references. This effect is reduced for V2 dataset that also measure stronger winds on the northern region with respect to the V1. It is important to underline that these maps are calculated without using any co-location criteria of the measurements; the quantitative results of the intercomparison will be calculated on co-located measurements.

Figure 3.2.2.2: relative occurrence of a wind value in SPIRE, CYGNSS and ASCAT datasets.

Figure 3.2.2.3: SPIRE V1 data averages map (period 1st June-31st August 2021, no co-location).

Figure 3.2.2.4: SPIRE V2 data averages map (period 1st June-31st August 2021, no co-location).

Figure 3.2.2.5: CYGNSS data averages map (period 1st June- 31st August 2021, no co-location).

Figure 3.2.2.6: ASCAT data averages map (period 1st June- 31st August 2021, no co-location).

Figure 3.2.2.7: uncertainty-measurements scatterplot.

Figure 3.2.2.8: relative uncertainty-measurements scatterplot.

Figure 3.2.2.7 and Figure 3.2.2.8 show the datasets uncertainty-measurements scatterplots. SPIRE is characterized by several uncertainty traces, depending on the combination of antenna/satellite that collected the measurements. SPIRE dataset does not have measurements below 1.4 m/s, with an uncertainty value of 0.7 m/s (50%) and above 11.6 m/s with an uncertainty of 2.7 m/s (23%). CYGNSS data (orange dots) cover a larger interval of measurement values (from 0 to 40 m/s, not entirely showed in the plots); after an initial positive trend, the uncertainty trend is quite flat from 2 to 6 m/s of measurement range and increase for stronger winds, showing a linear trend from 7 m/s. ASCAT (red dots), as explained above, has a fixed uncertainty value assigned, equal to 1.13 m/s.

3.2.3 Co-location methods

The next step to the intercomparison exercise is to find the spatial and temporal co-located measurements from the datasets. The spatial and temporal threshold for coupling measurements will be assigned considering the spatial and temporal synoptic scale characterizing the wind speed on the ocean and trying to minimize the spatial and temporal distance and maximize the number of co-located observations. If more of one observation of one or both instruments are present in a certain collocation area respecting the temporal selection criteria, they are averaged together and considered as a unique measurement with uncertainty equal to the averaged uncertainty. This method avoids redundancy in the formation of the couples.

We searched co-located CYGNSS measurements within ± 0.23 deg of latitude/longitude (about 25 km) and within ± 15 minutes; the resulting spatial collocation area is about a 50 km side square centred on measurements. This co-location criteria are the same used in [RD-10]. The total number of couples formed according to the described criteria is 1519 for V1 and 1147 for V2, their location is shown in Figure 3.2.3.1 for V1 and Figure 3.2.3.2 for V2. Figure 3.2.3.3 shows the number of co-located couples found on each day of the intercomparison period on the entire intercomparison region. SPIRE V1 is represented by blue and red dots, while SPIRE V2 is represented by green and red stars; red markers highlight the days with no couples. The larger part of the intercomparison period is covered

by at least one couple of co-located measurements, with the exception of the first part of June and July for V2, due to the lower number of couples found.

Figure 3.2.3.1: SPIRE V1 and CYGNSS co-located measurements.

Figure 3.2.3.2: SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS co-located measurements.

Figure 3.2.3.3: number of couples SPIRE - CYGNSS vs time.

For ASCAT, the spatial and temporal thresholds are 25 km and 60 minutes for V1. The larger time scale has been chosen for granting a number of couples similar to the CYGNSS case, 1435. Couples position is showed in Figure 3.2.3.4. Co-located observations are distributed in 23 days, as can be seen in Figure 3.2.3.6; this number could be increased with a different choice of the temporal and spatial thresholds, (e.g., 40 days using 120 minutes and 100 km) but at the cost of increasing the effect of the spatial and temporal distance on the intercomparison. V2 datasets presents a larger occurrence of couples with ASCAT so we decided to maintain the 15 minutes temporal threshold as for CYGNSS and as suggested by [RD-10]. Even with this reduced threshold V2-ASCAT couples are 2629, evenly spread during the intercomparison period (Figure 3.2.3.5). Again, the dots are used for V1 and stars for V2, with red markers showing the days with no couples.

Figure 3.2.3.4: SPIRE V1 and ASCAT co-located measurements.

Figure 3.2.3.5: SPIRE V2 and ASCAT co-located measurements.

Figure 3.2.3.6: number of couples SPIRE - ASCAT vs time

Hereinafter the results presented in the study (scatterplot, qq-plot, temporal and spatial analysis) will employ just co-located measurements.

3.2.4 SPIRE vs CYGNSS results

In this paragraph the results of SPIRE and CYGNSS wind speed intercomparison will be discussed.

3.2.4.1 Spatial and temporal analysis

The following plots show a spatial and temporal analysis of SPIRE-CYGNSS comparison. Figure 3.2.4.1 and Figure 3.2.4.2 show the spatial distribution of the number of couples. The intercomparison region has been divided into sectors of 2 deg in latitude and 5 deg in longitude; the number of couples found in each sector during the entire intercomparison period is showed by the colour scale.

Figure 3.2.4.1: SPIRE V1-CYGNSS spatial distribution of the number of couples.

Figure 3.2.4.2: SPIRE V2-CYGNSS spatial distribution of the number of couples.

Figure 3.2.4.3 and Figure 3.2.4.5 show the daily averages of the SPIRE (blue) and CYGNSS (orange) results for V1 and V2 respectively. Each dot represents the average value of the co-located measurements collected during a certain day on the entire intercomparison region, while the shaded area represents the daily average of the uncertainty of measurements. The two set of measurements are generally within their respective uncertainty, with few exceptions, e.g., mid-July for V1 and late August for V2.

Figure 3.2.4.4 and Figure 3.2.4.6 show the absolute and relative difference between the V1 and V2 timeseries. The zero-difference line is marked in orange and the shaded area represent the difference uncertainty. The maximum difference in this temporal analysis is with very few exceptions within 2.6 m/s, and within the difference uncertainty. The few significant differences revealed (greater than uncertainty) are on 3rd, 8th, and 21st June and on 5th August for V1, due probably to the low number of couples found on these days,

as can be seen in Figure 3.2.3.3. The V2 timeseries shows significant differences on July 9th and August 25th and 30th, all days characterized by a low number of couples.

Figure 3.2.4.3: daily averages of SPIRE V1 and CYGNSS measurements (spatially averaged on the entire intercomparison region).

Figure 3.2.4.4: temporal differences between SPIRE V1 and CYGNSS datasets (averaged spatially).

Figure 3.2.4.5: daily averages of SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS measurements (spatially averaged on the entire intercomparison region).

Figure 3.2.4.6: temporal differences between SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS datasets (averaged spatially).

Figure 3.2.4.7 and Figure 3.2.4.8 show the maps of SPIRE V1 and CYGNSS measurements. These graphs have been built averaging together all co-located measurements in 2 deg latitude and 5 deg longitude pixels collected during the entire intercomparison period. Both satellites observe a region characterized by lower winds on the equator; a stronger winds region emerges observing CYGNSS measurement on the south hemisphere that is not so clearly evident in SPIRE measurements. The difference in the southern region is within -2 m/s (-21%), as can be seen in Figure 3.2.4.9 and Figure 3.2.4.10; another evident feature is the positive peak (+1.6 m/s, +38%) in the northern region, in which SPIRE measures stronger winds with respect to CYGNSS.

The spatial results for V2 are reported in Figure 3.2.4.11 and Figure 3.2.4.12. The differences between satellites are reduced with respect to V1. SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS identify both a stronger wind region on the south, with CYGNSS presenting even higher wind speed and a calm region at the equator. Both missions also identify the relative minimum in the north. Differences, represented in Figure 3.2.4.13 and Figure 3.2.4.14, are reduced with respect to the V1 comparison, within -1.6 m/s (-18%, minimum in the south) to 1.4 m/s (23%, northern region).

Figure 3.2.4.7: SPIRE V1 map.

Figure 3.2.4.8: CYGNSS map (co-located with SPIRE V1).

Figure 3.2.4.9: SPIRE V1 vs CYGNSS difference map.

Figure 3.2.4.10: SPIRE V1 vs CYGNSS relative difference map.

Figure 3.2.4.11: SPIRE V2 map.

Figure 3.2.4.12: CYGNSS map (co-located with SPIRE V2).

Figure 3.2.4.13: SPIRE V2 vs CYGNSS difference map.

Figure 3.2.4.14: SPIRE V2 vs CYGNSS relative difference map.

In order to evaluate the uncertainty of the two satellites the following plots report the maps calculated averaging the uncertainties of measurements in the same pixel. Figure 3.2.4.15 and Figure 3.2.4.16 show the uncertainty maps of SPIRE and CYGNSS respectively for V1, Figure 3.2.4.17 and Figure 3.2.4.18 for V2, with numerical results reported in Table 1. No particular differences can be noted for spatial uncertainty analysis between the two versions. CYGNSS uncertainties are generally lower with respect to SPIRE ones.

Table 1: SPIRE vs CYGNSS uncertainty spatial analysis results.

BIAS analysis	Mean [m/s]	St. dev. [m/s]	Min [m/s]	Max [m/s]
SPIRE V1	1.65	0.21	1.17	2.08
CYGNSS (V1)	0.96	0.05	0.86	1.11
SPIRE V2	1.69	0.25	1.20	2.49
CYGNSS (V2)	0.95	0.05	0.87	1.09

Figure 3.2.4.15: SPIRE V1 uncertainty map.

Figure 3.2.4.16: CYGNSS (co-located SPIRE V1) uncertainty map.

Figure 3.2.4.17: SPIRE V2 uncertainty map.

Figure 3.2.4.18: CYGNSS (co-located SPIRE V2) uncertainty map.

Figure 3.2.4.19 and Figure 3.2.4.20 report the ratio between the measurements difference and the difference uncertainty. This plot is useful to individuate regions in which the difference is larger than the uncertainty (values above 1). All spatial differences are within their combined uncertainty, even the southern region and the northern peak. Finally, Figure 3.2.4.21 and Figure 3.2.4.22 show the ratio between SPIRE and CYGNSS uncertainties for V1 and V2 respectively: SPIRE generally has a higher uncertainty calculated, with an average ratio equal to 1.72 and standard deviation equal to 0.18. The V2 presents higher maximum of SPIRE uncertainty, even if the mean value of the two maps is quite similar (see Table 1).

Figure 3.2.4.19: ratio between SPIRE V1 vs CYGNSS difference and difference uncertainty.

Figure 3.2.4.20: ratio between SPIRE V2 vs CYGNSS difference and difference uncertainty.

Figure 3.2.4.21: ratio between SPIRE V1 and CYGNSS uncertainties.

Figure 3.2.4.22: ratio between SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS uncertainties.

3.2.4.2 Statistical analysis

Figure 3.2.4.23 shows the scatter plot between CYGNSS (x axis) and SPIRE V1 (y axis) measurements. The fit results and bias analysis of the two datasets is reported in Table 2. The two versions present similar results in all but the mean bias that is almost negligible for V2.

Table 2: SPIRE vs CYGNSS bias analysis.

	SPIRE V1 - CYGNSS	SPIRE V2 - CYGNSS
Number of couples	1519	1147
Fit slope	0.65	0.68
Fit intercept	2.00 m/s	2.02 m/s
Correlation Coefficient	0.77	0.80
Bias Mean value	-0.32 m/s	0.01 m/s
Bias Standard deviation	1.26 m/s	1.21 m/s
Mean difference uncertainty	1.90 m/s	1.92 m/s

Figure 3.2.4.23: SPIRE V1 vs CYGNSS scatterplot.

Figure 3.2.4.24: SPIRE V2 vs CYGNSS scatterplot.

Figure 3.2.4.25 and Figure 3.2.4.26 shows the measurements distribution of SPIRE and CYGNSS co-located couples in terms of relative occurrences of a certain measurement result (bin width equal to 1 m/s). For V1, as seen in Figure 3.2.2.2, SPIRE and CYGNSS distributions differ in the right tail, for values larger than 8 m/s. This discrepancy is reduced in V2.

Figure 3.2.4.27 and Figure 3.2.4.28 reports the result of the quantile-quantile plot, a statistical instrument that can be employed to visually investigate the distribution of the two datasets. In the left panel each dataset (blue for SPIRE, orange for CYGNSS) has been compared with the gaussian distribution that best fits its measurements, represented by the blue and red lines for SPIRE and CYGNSS datasets respectively. In the y-axis the values of measurements are represented, while the x-axis represents the values of a gaussian distribution expressed in terms of number of standard deviations. This graphical analysis highlights that SPIRE datasets tends to move away from the Gaussian distribution for wind values higher than 8 m/s. In particular the shape of the blue curve can be associated with a distribution with a right tail thinner with respect to a gaussian distribution.

The second panel is an inter-comparison of the distribution of the two datasets. The distribution of the quantiles of the two instruments reveals that the two datasets have a similar statistical distribution for the central part of the measurement spectrum, from 2.5 to 7.5 m/s, while SPIRE distribution tails are thinner with respect to CYGNSS. The comparison between versions reveals a graph closer to the ideal line for V2, indicating a reduced bias.

Figure 3.2.4.25: SPIRE V1 and CYGNSS co-located measurements histogram.

Figure 3.2.4.26: SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS co-located measurements histogram.

Figure 3.2.4.27: SPIRE V1 vs CYGNSS qq plots; (left) comparison of the two datasets with the gaussian theoretical distribution, (right) comparison of SPIRE and CYGNSS data distribution.

Figure 3.2.4.28: SPIRE V2 vs CYGNSS qq plots; (left) comparison of the two datasets with the gaussian theoretical distribution, (right) comparison of SPIRE and CYGNSS data distribution.

Figure 3.2.4.29 and Figure 3.2.4.30 show the differences plotted against CYGNSS measurement results (orange dots) and the mean and standard deviation of this difference. These last two quantities have been calculated dividing the measurements value in bins of 1 m/s of thickness and calculating the statistics of the values within each bin. This kind of plot is useful to observe the bias distribution with respect of the measurements. In particular this graph shows a negative bias more pronounced for larger values of wind speed and positive bias for lower wind. V2 bias presents positive values for winds until 7 m/s and negative bias for higher winds. The figures reveal that V2 bias has a similar shape of V1, but it is positive shifted, giving the small mean bias reported in Table 2 (V1 average values are plotted in Figure 3.2.4.30 for a visual comparison). Figure 3.2.4.31 reports the number of couples for each bin; bins with a low number of measurements, should be taken into consideration carefully due to the introduction of statistical oscillations.

Figure 3.2.4.29: SPIRE V1-CYGNSS differences vs CYGNSS measurements.

Figure 3.2.4.30: SPIRE V2-CYGNSS differences vs CYGNSS measurements.

Figure 3.2.4.31: number of couples per bin (bin width 1 m/s).

Figure 3.2.4.32: SPIRE-CYGNSS difference histogram

Figure 3.2.4.33: V1 histogram of ratio between difference and difference uncertainty. The coloured area is reported in the legend.

Figure 3.2.4.34: V2 histogram of ratio between difference and difference uncertainty. The coloured area is reported in the legend.

Figure 3.2.4.32 shows the histogram of the differences between SPIRE and CYGNSS and the results of gaussian fits (dashed lines). The histogram bins width is 0.5 m/s; the V1 gaussian fit is centred at -0.12 m/s with a sigma of 1.19 m/s, while V2 fit has 0,01 m/s as mean value and sigma 1.11 m/s; these values are indicative of the mean bias and

uncertainty characterizing the distributions and are related to the mean bias and standard deviation shown in Table 2. The discrepancy between the numbers is probably due to the non-perfect gaussian distribution of the differences for both versions. The sigma found with fit is lower with respect to the dataset mean uncertainty (1.90 and 1,92 m/s); this imply that the larger part of the differences will be within the measurement uncertainty.

This is confirmed by Figure 3.2.4.33 and Figure 3.2.4.34, that show the histograms of the values of the ratio between SPIRE-CYGNSS differences and difference uncertainty. Histograms has been built using 0.25 width bins. Observing V1, the larger part of the couples present differences within their combined uncertainty (green area, 87.2% of the total couples). The cyan and purple areas referring to significative negative differences represent the 10.8% of the total, while the yellow and red areas, referring to significative positive differences, the 2.0%. V2 distributions is better centred on zero difference, with 90.3% of values in the non-significative difference area and the rest distributed on the tails with the positive tail slight thinner of the negative tail (6.1% versus 3.6%).

Figure 3.2.4.35 and Figure 3.2.4.36 show the ratio between differences and combined uncertainties ($r = \Delta/\sigma$) as function of the CYGNSS measurement values (blue dots). The bins in this analysis are the same of those used for Figure 3.2.4.29. The purple curve represents the average of the ratios calculated within a certain measurement bin (bins widths equal to 1 m/s), with the standard deviation shown by the purple area (Figure 3.2.4.36 displays the average values of both version for a better visual comparison). V2 mean values show a similar shape with respect to V1, with a positive shift on the y axis.

Figure 3.2.4.35: V1 study of the ratio between differences and uncertainties as function of CYGNSS measurements.

Figure 3.2.4.36: V2 study of the ratio between differences and uncertainties as function of CYGNSS measurements.

Figure 3.2.4.37: percentage of measurements with $r > 1$ as function of the reference wind speed.

The frequency of significant differences is displayed by the histogram in Figure 3.2.4.37; the larger part of SPIRE measurement spectrum (from 1 to 10 m/s) have a mean r value within the range of non-significant difference $[-1, 1]$. The higher winds are, however, characterized by negative differences that became more significant with the increasing of the wind speed. For V1, the occurrence of significant differences shown by the histogram reaches the minimum values of 2.9% for the 4-5 m/s bin and is within 17% in the region from 1 to 9 m/s; the frequency increases for the region between 9 and 12 m/s (the first and last bin should be not taken into account due to the very low number of measurements located there, 4 and 2 respectively, see also Figure 3.2.4.31). V2 has less significant differences for higher winds but more occurrence in the low wind part of the plot. Globally the total percentage of significant difference is slight decreased (as seen in the previous plots). The minimum of significant difference is 3.5% in the 7-8 m/s bin, the percentage remains within 15% in the range 1-9 m/s (with the exception of the 0-1 m/s bin in which the percentage is 100% but the number of measurements in this bin is just 5), and the percentage increases to 62% for higher winds.

3.2.5 SPIRE vs ASCAT results

In this paragraph the results of SPIRE and ASCAT wind speed intercomparison will be discussed.

3.2.5.1 Spatial and temporal analysis.

The following plots show the spatial and temporal analysis of SPIRE and ASCAT measurements. Figure 3.2.5.1 Figure 3.2.5.2 show the spatial distribution of the number of couples. As done for CYGNSS, the intercomparison region has been divided into sectors of 2 deg in latitude and 5 deg in longitude. V2 presents a larger number of couples, spread during the intercomparison period, as shown in Figure 3.2.3.6.

Figure 3.2.5.1: V1 spatial distribution of the number of couples.

Figure 3.2.5.2: V2 spatial distribution of the number of couples.

Figure 3.2.5.3: daily averages of SPIRE-V1 and ASCAT measurements (spatially averaged on the entire intercomparison region).

Figure 3.2.5.4: daily averages of SPIRE-V2 and ASCAT measurements (spatially averaged on the entire intercomparison region).

Figure 3.2.5.3 and Figure 3.2.5.4 show the daily averages of the SPIRE (blue) and ASCAT (red) results. Each dot represents the average value of the co-located measurements collected during a certain day on the entire intercomparison region, while shaded area is the daily average of the uncertainty of measurements. Unfortunately, SPIRE V1-ASCAT couples are focused on a limited number of days (first days of June, second part of June, second part of July and second part of August), while V2 couples are spread during the entire intercomparison period. Both V1 and V2 and ASCAT timeseries are generally within their respective uncertainty.

Figure 3.2.5.5 and Figure 3.2.5.6 show the absolute and relative difference between the SPIRE and ASCAT timeseries. The zero-difference line is marked in orange and the shaded area represent the difference uncertainty. The difference in this temporal analysis is within [0.6, -1.9] m/s and [13, -25] % (minimum, maximum values) for V1 and [1.6, -2.3] m/s and [35, -22]%, for V2. Both versions are within the difference uncertainty with ASCAT reference.

Figure 3.2.5.5: temporal differences between SPIRE V1 and CYGNSS datasets (averaged spatially).

Figure 3.2.5.6: temporal differences between SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS datasets (averaged spatially).

Figure 3.2.5.7 and Figure 3.2.5.8 show the maps of SPIRE-V1 and ASCAT measurements. These graphs have been built averaging together all co-located measurements in a certain region (2 deg latitude and 5 deg longitude) collected during the entire intercomparison period. Some map pixels are left empty due to the lack of couples in those regions.

The observed structures are similar to those seen in the CYGNSS comparison; both satellites observe lower winds on the equator and a stronger winds region on the south hemisphere. The difference between the two maps tends to concentrate on pixels characterized by stronger winds, with SPIRE lower than ASCAT, as can be seen in Figure 3.2.5.9 and Figure 3.2.5.10. The difference is within [0.9, -2.2] m/s and [13, -22] %.

Figure 3.2.5.7: SPIRE V1 map in correspondence of co-located ASCAT measurements.

Figure 3.2.5.8: ASCAT map in correspondence of co-located SPIRE V1 measurements.

Figure 3.2.5.9: SPIRE V1 vs ASCAT co-located difference map.

Figure 3.2.5.10: SPIRE V1 vs ASCAT co-located relative difference map.

Figure 3.2.5.11 and Figure 3.2.5.12 show the maps of SPIRE-V2 and ASCAT measurements. Even in this version satellites observe lower winds on the equator and a stronger winds region on the south hemisphere. The wind showed in both SPIRE V2 and ASCAT in the northern region are more pronounced with respect to V1, but this can be also due to the different time/space distribution of the couples. The differences are more significant on tiles characterized by stronger winds, as in V1, but they are less pronounced with respect to V1, as can be seen in Figure 3.2.5.13 and Figure 3.2.5.14. The difference is within [1.7, -0.9] m/s and [27, -11] %, with a mean value of 0.10 m/s and a standard deviation of 0.57 m/s.

Figure 3.2.5.11: SPIRE V2 map in correspondence of co-located ASCAT measurements.

Figure 3.2.5.12: ASCAT map in correspondence of co-located SPIRE V2 measurements.

Figure 3.2.5.13: SPIRE V2 vs ASCAT co-located difference map.

Figure 3.2.5.14: SPIRE V2 vs ASCAT co-located relative difference map.

Table 3: uncertainty spatial analysis results.

	Mean [m/s]	St. dev. [m/s]	Min [m/s]	Max [m/s]
SPIRE V1	1.63	0.24	1.10	2.25
ASCAT (V1)	1.13	0.00	1.13	1.13
SPIRE V2	1.99	0.31	1.25	2.74
ASCAT (V2)	1.13	0.00	1.13	1.13

In order to evaluate the uncertainty of the two satellites the following plots report the uncertainty maps. Figure 3.2.5.15, Figure 3.2.5.16 and Figure 3.2.5.17 show the uncertainty maps of SPIRE V1, V2 and ASCAT respectively, with numerical results reported in Table 3. ASCAT uncertainty has a constant value, assigned using the ASCAT intercomparison report, as explained in the introduction. SPIRE V2 uncertainty tends to be larger with respect to V1 (0.36 m/s difference), maybe due to the different distribution of couples with time.

Figure 3.2.5.15: SPIRE-V1 uncertainty map (co-located ASCAT).

Figure 3.2.5.16: SPIRE-V2 uncertainty map (co-located ASCAT).

Figure 3.2.5.17: ASCAT uncertainty map (constant and equal for V1 and V2).

Figure 3.2.5.18 and Figure 3.2.5.19 report the ratio between the measurements difference and the difference uncertainty. Spatial differences are within their combined uncertainty (ratio lower than 1), even for V1 in the southern region in which the difference is more pronounced, with V2 values lower. Figure 3.2.5.20 and Figure 3.2.5.21 show the ratio between SPIRE and ASCAT uncertainties. Uncertainty ratio is within [1.0, 2.0] for V1 and [1.1, 2.4] for V2 with SPIRE2 uncertainty generally higher; average uncertainty is 1.44 for V1 and 1.76 for V2, with standard difference equal to 0.21 for V1 and 0.27 for V2.

Figure 3.2.5.18: ratio between SPIRE V1 vs ASCAT difference and difference uncertainty.

Figure 3.2.5.19: ratio between SPIRE V2 vs ASCAT difference and difference uncertainty.

Figure 3.2.5.20: ratio between SPIRE V1 and ASCAT co-located uncertainties.

Figure 3.2.5.21: ratio between SPIRE V2 and ASCAT co-located uncertainties.

3.2.5.2 Statistical analysis

Figure 3.2.5.22 shows the scatter plot between ASCAT (x axis) and SPIRE V1 (y axis) measurements, while V2 scatterplot is in Figure 3.2.5.23; the linear regression results and bias analysis of the two datasets is reported in Table 4. V2 version is characterized by an almost negligible bias with respect to V1, a slightly larger standard deviation and mean difference uncertainty.

Table 4: SPIRE vs ASCAT bias analysis.

	SPIRE V1 - ASCAT	SPIRE V2 - ASCAT
Number of couples	1435	2629
Fit slope	0.70	0.70
Fit intercept	1.54 m/s	1.98 m/s
Correlation Coefficient	0.81	0.80
Mean value	-0.44 m/s	-0.05 m/s
Standard deviation	1.03 m/s	1.12 m/s
Mean difference uncertainty	1.98 m/s	2.29 m/s

Figure 3.2.5.22: SPIRE V1 vs ASCAT scatterplot.

Figure 3.2.5.23: SPIRE V2 vs ASCAT scatterplot.

Figure 3.2.5.24: SPIRE V1 and ASCAT co-located measurements histogram.

Figure 3.2.5.25: SPIRE V2 and ASCAT co-located measurements histogram.

In Figure 3.2.5.24 and Figure 3.2.5.25, the measurements distribution of SPIRE and ASCAT co-located couples in terms of relative occurrences of a certain measurement result is reported (bin width equal to 1 m/s). As seen in CYGNSS intercomparison, V1

distribution differs in the right tail with respect to ASCAT, for values larger than 8 m/s, while V2 presents a similar shape with respect to V1 but is shifted towards positive values, leading to a better agreement with ASCAT.

The result of the quantile-quantile plot is in Figure 3.2.5.26 and Figure 3.2.5.27. In the left panel each dataset (blue for SPIRE, red for ASCAT) has been compared with the gaussian distribution that best fits its measurements, represented by the blue and orange lines for SPIRE and ASCAT datasets respectively. As seen in CYGNSS, SPIRE dataset tends to move away from the Gaussian distribution for wind values higher than 8 m/s, resulting in a distribution with thinner tails and confirming the consideration made above. ASCAT moves away from the gaussian for lower values of wind, below 4 m/s.

The second panel is an inter-comparison of the distribution of the two datasets. The distribution of the quantiles of the two instruments is represented by the dots while the red line represents the ideal agreement of the two distributions. The panel reveals a more pronounced bias with respect of those found for CYGNSS, in which we found a better agreement in the central part of the measurement spectrum. The curve shape indicates also that SPIRE distribution tails are thinner with respect to ASCAT ones. Both V1 and V2 present a similar shape and the principal difference seems to be a positive offset for the V2 that reduces the discrepancy with respect of the ideal agreement.

Figure 3.2.5.26: SPIRE V1 vs ASCAT qq-plots; (left) comparison of the two datasets with the gaussian theoretical distribution, (right) comparison of SPIRE and ASCAT data distribution.

Figure 3.2.5.27: SPIRE V2 vs ASCAT qq-plots; (left) comparison of the two datasets with the gaussian theoretical distribution, (right) comparison of SPIRE and ASCAT data distribution.

Figure 3.2.5.28: SPIRE-ASCAT differences vs ASCAT measurements.

Figure 3.2.5.29: SPIRE-ASCAT differences vs ASCAT measurements.

In Figure 3.2.5.28 and Figure 3.2.5.29 the differences between SPIRE and ASCAT plotted against ASCAT measurement results (red dots), and the mean and standard deviation of this difference are reported. These last two quantities have been calculated dividing the

measurements value in bins of 1 m/s of thickness and calculating the statistics of values within that bin. The graph displays a negative bias more pronounced for larger values of wind speed, a negligible bias in the central part of the measurement spectrum (3-6 m/s) and positive bias for lower wind; this last information should be considered carefully due to the low number of measurements, showed in the histogram of Figure 3.2.5.30. V2 analysis reveals the same features of V1 but a better acknowledgement with ASCAT above 8 m/s and a positive bias (larger of V1) below this value. In Figure 3.2.5.29 is reported the V1 average bias for a visual comparison.

Figure 3.2.5.30: SPIRE-ASCAT number of measurements per bin (bin width 1 m/s).

Figure 3.2.5.31: SPIRE V1-ASCAT difference histogram

Figure 3.2.5.31 shows the histogram of the differences between SPIRE and ASCAT and the result of the gaussian fit (dashed lines). Histogram bins width is 0.5 m/s; the fit gaussian is centred at -0.45 m/s with a sigma of 0.97 m/s for V1 and -0.01 m/s with a sigma of 1.04 m/s; these values are indicative of the mean bias and uncertainty characterizing the distribution and are related to the mean difference and standard deviation shown in Table 4. The discrepancy between the numbers is probably due to the non-perfect gaussian distribution of the differences. As in CYGNSS case, the sigma found with fit is lower with respect to the dataset mean uncertainty (1.98 m/s) indicating that the larger part of the differences will be within the difference uncertainty.

Figure 3.2.5.32 and Figure 3.2.5.33 are the histogram of the ratio $r = \Delta/\sigma$ between SPIRE-ASCAT differences and difference uncertainty; histogram has been built using 0.25 width bins. The larger part of V1 couples present differences within their combined uncertainty (green area, 91.4% of the total couples). The cyan and purple areas referring to significative negative differences represent the 7.5% of the total, while the yellow and red areas, referring to significative positive differences, the 1.2%. The V2 measurements have an even larger green area, 96.1%, and more symmetry between tails.

Figure 3.2.5.32: histogram of ratio between difference and uncertainty for V1.

Figure 3.2.5.33: histogram of ratio between difference and uncertainty for V2.

Figure 3.2.5.34: study of the ratio between V1 and ASCAT differences and uncertainties as function of ASCAT measurements.

Figure 3.2.5.35: study of the ratio between V2 and ASCAT differences and uncertainties as function of ASCAT measurements.

Figure 3.2.5.36: occurrence of significant differences per wind speed bin.

Figure 3.2.5.34 and Figure 3.2.5.35 are a study of r (blue dots) as function of ASCAT measurements. The bins in this analysis are the same of those used for Figure 3.2.5.30. The purple and green curves represent the average of the ratios calculated within a certain measurement bin (bins widths equal to 1 m/s), with the standard deviation shown by the shaded area. The frequency of significant differences is displayed by Figure 3.2.5.36.

The larger part of SPIRE measurement spectrum (from 1 to 10 m/s) have a mean r value within the range of non-significative difference $[-1, 1]$. The higher winds are, however, characterized by negative differences that became more significative with the increasing of the wind speed. For V1, the occurrences of significative differences shown by the histogram reach the minimum values of 0% for the 3-4 m/s bin and are within 10% in the region from 1 to 9 m/s. The frequency increases for the region between 9 and 12 m/s, reaching the totally of the measurements contained in the 12-13 m/s bin. V2 minimum is at 7-8 m/s bin with an increase of significative differences in the higher wind bins less pronounced with respect to V1; the comparison also reveals an increased number of significative differences at the 1-2 m/s bin. The frequency of the first and last bin should be not considered due to the very low number of measurements located there.

3.2.6 SPIRE vs TAO

The TAO array (renamed the TAO/TRITON array on 1 January 2000) consists of approximately 70 moorings in the Tropical Pacific Ocean, telemetering oceanographic and meteorological data to shore in real-time via the Argos satellite system. The array is a major component of the El Niño/Southern Oscillation (ENSO) Observing System, the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) and the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS). Moorings are positioned as showed in Figure 1.3.5.1 and measure the ocean surface wind intensity and direction with a temporal resolution of 10 minutes.

SPIRE, ASCAT and CYGNSS measurements have been compared with ground measurements from TAO array for each mooring available in the intercomparison region. The spatial and temporal thresholds selected for the intercomparison are ± 0.23 deg in latitude and longitude (about 25 km) and ± 5 minutes (the half of the ground reference time frequency). This short temporal threshold has been selected due to the high time frequency of ground reference to avoid ambiguity in the comparison: a satellite measurement can be co-located with just one ground measurements. If more than one satellite measurement is within the co-location criteria, the ground measurements will be confronted with their average, with uncertainty assigned equal to the average uncertainty.

Figure 3.2.6.1: satellites vs TAO scatterplot (all buoys together).

The number of SPIRE passages over the ground sites selected during the three months of intercomparison is 81 for V1 and 93 for V2, resulting in few numbers of co-located measurements per site. As in the ASCAT intercomparison this number should be doubled with the doubling of the spatial threshold, but we decided to employ the same value of the other intercomparison for consistency. This low number do not permit to make a significative statistical analysis of the single sites, but we can put together all the results to compare SPIRE measurements versus the entire buoys array. In the Appendix we will also

present the results of the single sites to make a qualitative comparison with the available co-located measurements. The total numbers of co-located couple of CYGNSS and ASCAT are 1755 and 1160 respectively, suggesting the larger capability of these two satellites of cover the selected region.

The direct comparison between SPIRE, CYGNSS and ASCAT and TAO statistical results should be considered carefully, due to the different number of couples of the three datasets and to the fact that the three satellites have been co-located separately with TAO measurements, resulting in different measurement conditions. The authors, however, believe that presenting the results of the reference satellites provide a deeper knowledge of the capability of SPIRE.

Figure 3.2.6.1 shows the scatterplot between satellites and TAO measurements. SPIRE data are marked with larger dots in blue and green for V1 and V2 respectively. The fit results are reported in Table 5 and the bias analysis is reported in Table 6. SPIRE V1 and V2 present a correlation coefficient lower with respect to the other two satellites, maybe also due to the low number of couples considered in the fit. A bias of -0.69 m/s with a mean difference uncertainty of 1.6 m/s, larger with respect of other two satellites is calculated for V1. V2 has a larger number of couples (93), its bias is reduced to -0.18 m/s with an uncertainty of 1.89 m/s, while other parameters remain similar to those of V1. CYGNSS and ASCAT do not show a significative bias. Bias standard deviations found are comparable for V1 and V2, CYGNSS standard deviation is 1.13 m/s, while ASCAT presents a lower value of 0.88 m/s.

Table 5: fit results (all buoys).

Satellite	Slope	Intercept [m/s]	correlation	number
SPIRE V1	0.64	1.72	0.73	81
SPIRE V2	0.68	1.98	0.74	93
CYGNSS	0.84	1.12	0.78	1755
ASCAT	0.88	0.81	0.87	1160

Table 6: Satellites vs TAO bias analysis (all buoys).

	Bias [m/s]	Bias std [m/s]	Bias unc [m/s]	num
SPIRE V1	-0.69	1.21	1.63	81
SPIRE V2	-0.18	1.29	1.89	93
CYGNSS	-0.005	1.13	1.08	1755
ASCAT	-0.03	0.88	1.21	1160

Figure 3.2.6.2: satellites vs TAO distribution of measurements.

Figure 3.2.6.2 shows the distribution of measurements of the co-located couples. The SPIRE measurements are in blue and green for V1 and V2 respectively, the other two satellites are in orange and red; the respective co-located TAO measurements distributions are plotted with a dashed line of the same colour. CYGNSS and ASCAT do not reveal particular difference with respect of their co-located TAO measurements, while SPIRE V1 displays less measurements of wind above 7.5 m/s and larger number for lower speed. SPIRE V1 - TAO distribution shows a peak at 6.5 m/s while the other distributions are both centred on 7.5 m/s. SPIRE V2 distribution is similar to CYGNSS and ASCAT ones, but its co-located TAO distribution (green dashed line) reveals a double peak, with its absolute maximum in the 6-7 m/s bin like the co-located V1 TAO. This peak, shared by both V1 and V2 should be due to the particular spatial and temporal distribution of the co-located couples and is shifted with respect of the distributions of TAO associated with CYGNSS and ASCAT. V2 differs from TAO co-located distribution principally in the 7-8 m/s bin (greater than TAO value) and in 6-7 m/s bin (lower than TAO value).

Figure 3.2.6.3 displays the qq-plot between the satellites and their co-located measurements. CYGNSS and ASCAT have similar data distribution of their co-located ground measurements, while SPIRE distributions tend to move away from TAO, in particular for higher winds. V2 presents generally higher values with respect to V1, leading its result to be closer to CYGNSS and ASCAT, although even V2 reveals a negative bias for winds above 9 m/s less pronounced than V1.

Figure 3.2.6.3: satellites vs TAO qq-plots.

Figure 3.2.6.4: differences versus ground measurements.

Figure 3.2.6.4 shows the differences as function of the ground measurement. SPIRE V1 and V2 results are represented as small dots blue and green respectively; as in the previous intercomparison the differences have been divided in bins by their measurement value with width equal to 1 m/s. Large dots represent the mean difference of each bin and the coloured area the standard deviation. CYGNSS and ASCAT do not show pronounced bias values with the exception of CYGNSS in the lower and upper part of the measurement

spectrum. The V1/V2 plot reveals a bias that decreases from 1.3/0.8 m/s of the 2-3 m/s bin to -2.4/-1.8 of the 10-11 m/s. The number of measurements per bin is reported in Figure 3.2.6.5 and Figure 3.2.6.6 (focused on SPIRE measurements only). Although the low numbers on which the bias analysis is based, SPIRE bias shows a similar shape with respect of those found for the ASCAT and CYGNSS intercomparison studies, with V2 mean bias shifted with respect to V1 towards positive values (with the exception of the value at 2-3 m/s bin, maybe influenced by the low number of measurements of the bin).

Figure 3.2.6.5: number of measurements per bin.

Figure 3.2.6.6: number of measurements per bin (focus on SPIRE datasets).

Figure 3.2.6.7 represents the differences (satellites-TAO) histogram (solid lines) and their gaussian fits (dashed lines); fit means and standard deviations are reported in Table 7. CYGNSS and ASCAT have a gaussian shape centred on the zero difference, while SPIRE has more peaks, maybe due to the low number of couples. SPIRE V1 is centred on -0.77 m/s with a standard deviation of 1.18 m/s, while V2 mean is -0.30 m/s with standard deviation of 1.43 m/s; those are related to those reported in Table 6, with the differences caused by the deviation from gaussian distribution.

Table 7: gaussian fit results.

	Mean [m/s]	standard deviation [m/s]
SPIRE V1	-0.77	1.18
SPIRE V2	-0.30	1.43
CYGNSS	-0.07	1.07
ASCAT	-0.00	0.72

Figure 3.2.6.7: histogram of satellite-ground differences (solid lines) and gaussian fits (dashed lines).

Table 8: gaussian fit areas.

	$-1 \leq r \leq 1$	$r < -1$	$r > 1$
SPIRE V1	73%	23%	4%
SPIRE V2	82%	13%	5%
CYGNSS	69%	17%	14%
ASCAT	86%	8%	6%

Figure 3.2.6.8: histogram of difference/uncertainty ratio.

Figure 3.2.6.9: difference/uncertainty ratio versus ground measurements.

Figure 3.2.6.8 shows the difference/uncertainty ratio ($r = \Delta/\sigma$) histogram. As suggested by the gaussian fit in Figure 3.2.6.7, the distributions of both V1 and V2 are not centred on

$r = 0$, but presents a negative peak value. The percentage of measurements of SPIRE V1 with $-1 \leq r \leq 1$ is 73% (59 measurements), for V2 is 82% (76 measurements). The negative significant differences ($r < -1$) are the 23% of the total (19 measurements) for V1 and 13% (12 measurements) for V2 while the positive significant differences ($r > 1$) are 4% (3 measurements) for V1 and 5% (5 measurements) for V2. As in the previous intercomparison the negative significant differences are more common. A summary for the three satellites is in Table 8; both V1 and V2 presents a percentage of differences within the uncertainty higher with respect to CYGNSS, even due to the larger uncertainty of SPIRE dataset.

The plot of Δ/σ as function of TAO measurements is in Figure 3.2.6.9. As in Figure 3.2.6.4 the population of Δ/σ have been divided in 1 m/s bins and calculated the averages and standard deviation of each bin (large dots and shadow); SPIRE population is represented as small dots, blue for V1, green for V2. All the three satellites reveal a decrease of r with the increase of wind speed; SPIRE average r moves out from the non-significant difference region (e.g., [-1, 1]) for wind higher than 9 m/s. We see also a relative minimum of the average r in the 4-5 m/s bin for both versions, due to the presence of some outliers. The graph examined show that all satellites tend to overestimate lower wind and underestimate stronger wind, with SPIRE tending to have more significant negative differences with respect of the other two. CYGNSS mean r in Figure 3.2.6.9 presents a maximum in the 1-2 m/s bin due to the presence of an outlier and the few number of measurements of the bin (3 measurements).

Figure 3.2.6.10: histogram of the significant differences.

In Figure 3.2.6.10 we show the relative occurrence of significant differences in each bin. ASCAT is the satellite with lower occurrences. SPIRE V1 presents lower values with respect to CYGNSS for 4 to 8 m/s, with a minimum in the 5-6 m/s bin of 14.5% and a maximum that could be caused by the few number (5) of measurements. V2 has a larger percentage of significant differences in the 4-5 bin (45%) and in 6-7 bin (22%) but generally presents lower values with respect to V1.

3.3 SPIRE mss intercomparison

In this paragraph the intercomparison between SPIRE and CYGNSS mss is presented. SPIRE mss uncertainty is not present in the files nor values are given in the documentation, although a citation to [RD-5] is present. For these reasons the uncertainty of SPIRE will be treated as 0 in the calculations. The reference CYGNSS dataset is the Level 2 Science Data Record, Version 3.1. Versions 1 and 2 results will be presented.

3.3.1 Measurement screening

SPIRE measurements have been screened according to similar criteria used for the wind speed, through the quality flag and the variable *sm_quality_flags*. CYGNSS data have been screened according to the variable *mss_flag*.

Considering the entire SPIRE dataset, the number of rejected measurements is 120 on a total of 129004 measurements, less than 0.1% for V1 and 299 measurements of a total of 125441, about 0.2%, for V2.

3.3.2 Datasets general overview

Figure 3.3.2.1 and Figure 3.3.2.2 show the measurement absolute and relative histogram of SPIRE and CYGNSS datasets. These plots are obtained before built the co-located couples of measurements and give a general overview of the two datasets. As for the wind speed, CYGNSS presents a larger number of measurements, given by the larger number of satellite composing CYGNSS. This first analysis suggests a bias affecting the two datasets, that will be quantified in the co-located analysis.

The bias affecting the two datasets is evident in the Figure 3.3.2.3, Figure 3.3.2.4 and Figure 3.3.2.5 in which the maps of the average mss collected by the two satellites during the entire intercomparison period are presented.

Figure 3.3.2.1: mean square slope histogram.

Figure 3.3.2.2: mean square slope relative occurrence.

Figure 3.3.2.3: SPIRE V1 general map (average on the entire intercomparison period).

Figure 3.3.2.4: SPIRE V2 general map (average on the entire intercomparison period).

Figure 3.3.2.5: CYGNSS general map (average on the entire intercomparison period)

3.3.3 Co-location criteria

The co-location criteria used for the formation of the couples of measurements for the intercomparison is the same of those used for the wind speed study; co-located measurements within ± 0.23 deg of latitude/longitude (about 25 km) and within ± 15 minutes.

The resulting spatial colocation area is about a 50 km side square centred on measurements. The number of couples per day is showed in Figure 3.3.3.1, with the days with no couples marked in red. V1 is represented by blue and red dots and V2 is represented by green and red stars. The total number of couples formed according to the described criteria is 5561 for V1 and 4164 for V2, their location is showed in Figure 3.3.3.2

and Figure 3.3.3.3. If more of one observation of one or both instruments are present in a certain colocation area respecting the temporal selection criteria, they are averaged together and considered as a unique measurement with uncertainty equal to the averaged uncertainty to avoid redundancy in the formation of the couples.

All the following plots are referred to co-located couples of measurements. Due to the lack of SPIRE mss uncertainty all the evaluation of the difference will be based on CYGNSS uncertainty only (difference uncertainty equal to CYGNSS uncertainty).

Figure 3.3.3.1: SPIRE V1 – CYGNSS daily number of mss couples

Figure 3.3.3.2: SPIRE V1 CYGNSS co-located mss measurements.

Figure 3.3.3.3: SPIRE V2 CYGNSS co-located mss measurements.

3.3.4 SPIRE vs CYGNSS mss results

In this paragraph the results of SPIRE and CYGNSS mss intercomparison will be discussed.

3.3.4.1 Spatial and temporal analysis

The following plots show a spatial and temporal analysis of SPIRE and CYGNSS mss measurements.

Figure 3.3.4.1: mss V1 spatial distribution of the number of couples.

Figure 3.3.4.2: mss V2 spatial distribution of the number of couples.

Figure 3.3.4.1 and Figure 3.3.4.2 show the spatial distribution of the number of couples. The intercomparison region has been divided into sectors of 2 deg in latitude and 5 deg in longitude; the number of couples found in each sector during the entire intercomparison period is showed by the colour scale.

Figure 3.3.4.3: daily averages of SPIRE V1 and CYGNSS measurements (spatially averaged on the entire intercomparison region).

Figure 3.3.4.3 and Figure 3.3.4.5 show the daily averages of the SPIRE V1 and V2 respectively confronted with CYGNSS. Each dot represents the average value of the co-located measurements collected during a certain day on the entire intercomparison region. The shaded area represents the daily average of the uncertainty of measurements (averaged on the entire intercomparison region) and is present only for CYGNSS due to the lack of uncertainty for SPIRE. SPIRE dataset appears to be significantly lower for both V1 and V2, confirming bias in the datasets even if the two timeseries appear correlated.

Figure 3.3.4.4: temporal differences between SPIRE and CYGNSS datasets (averaged spatially).

Figure 3.3.4.5: daily averages of SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS measurements (spatially averaged on the entire intercomparison region).

Figure 3.3.4.6: temporal differences between SPIRE and CYGNSS datasets (averaged spatially).

Figure 3.3.4.4 and Figure 3.3.4.6 show the absolute and relative difference between SPIRE and CYGNSS timeseries for V1 and V2 respectively. The zero-difference line is marked in orange and the shaded area represent the difference uncertainty. The differences of V1 - CYGNSS are within [-0.018, 0.0] and [-67, 2] % (minimum, maximum values), with mean value -0.0062 (-30%) and standard deviation 0.0026 (11%). V2 differences are within [-

0.013, 0.002] and [-52, 14]%, with mean value -0.0058 and standard deviation of 0.0026. Generally, the differences are significant.

Figure 3.3.4.7 and Figure 3.3.4.8 show the maps of SPIRE V1 and CYGNSS measurements (bins of 2 deg latitude and 5 deg longitude), collected during the entire intercomparison period. Both satellites observe a minimum of mss on the equator with a higher mss on the south hemisphere. The difference between the two maps appears to be stronger on tiles characterized by higher mss, in particular in the south region, as seen in wind speed difference maps, Figure 3.3.4.9 and Figure 3.2.5.10. The difference is within [-0.010, 0.000] and [0, -46]%, with a mean value of -0.006 and a standard deviation of 0.002.

Figure 3.3.4.7: SPIRE V1 mss map in correspondence of co-located CYGNSS measurements.

Figure 3.3.4.8: CYGNSS mss map in correspondence of co-located SPIRE V1 measurements.

Figure 3.3.4.9: SPIRE V1 vs CYGNSS co-located difference map.

Figure 3.3.4.10: SPIRE V1 vs CYGNSS co-located relative difference map.

SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS co-located with V2 measurements are in Figure 3.3.4.11 and Figure 3.3.4.12. The structures emerging from the maps are similar to those of V1, with lower mss at equator and higher in the southern region. Even here the bias is evident. Differences, represented in Figure 3.3.4.13 and Figure 3.3.4.14 are within $[-0.011, 0.002]$ and $[-44, 8]\%$, with a mean value of -0.006 and standard deviation of 0.002 .

Figure 3.3.4.11: SPIRE V2 mss map in correspondence of co-located CYGNSS measurements.

Figure 3.3.4.12: CYGNSS mss map in correspondence of co-located SPIRE V2 measurements.

Figure 3.3.4.13: SPIRE V2 vs CYGNSS co-located difference map.

Figure 3.3.4.14: SPIRE V2 vs CYGNSS co-located relative difference map.

Table 9: mss uncertainty spatial analysis results.

	Mean	St. dev.	min	max
SPIRE V1/V2	0	0	0	0
CYGNSS (V1)	0.0039	0.0007	0.0025	0.0059
CYGNSS (V2)	0.0040	0.0008	0.0025	0.0079

Figure 3.3.4.15 and Figure 3.3.4.16 show the uncertainty maps of CYGNSS co-located with V1 and V2 respectively, with numerical results reported in Table 9.

Figure 3.3.4.15: CYGNSS (co-located V1) uncertainty map.

Figure 3.3.4.16: CYGNSS (co-located V2) uncertainty map.

Figure 3.3.4.17 and Figure 3.3.4.18 report the ratio between the satellites difference and the difference uncertainty. This plot is useful to individuate regions in which the difference is larger than the uncertainty (values above 1). The major part of spatial differences is significative.

Figure 3.3.4.17: ratio between SPIRE vs SPIRE V1 difference and difference uncertainty.

Figure 3.3.4.18: ratio between SPIRE vs SPIRE V2 difference and difference uncertainty.

3.3.4.2 Statistical analysis

Figure 3.3.4.19 and Figure 3.3.4.20 show the scatter plot between CYGNSS (x axis) and SPIRE (y axis) mss measurements for V1 and V2 respectively. The fit results and bias analysis of the two datasets is reported in Table 10. The mean difference between the datasets is equal to -0.0061, the mean relative difference is -28%, with a standard deviation of 0.0048 m/s for an average difference uncertainty of 0.0028 (from the single CYGNSS uncertainty); no significant improvement in V2 seems to emerge from the statistical parameters.

Table 10: SPIRE vs CYGNSS mss bias analysis.

Mss	SPIRE V1 - CYGNSS	SPIRE V2 - CYGNSS
Number of couples	5561	4164
Fit slope	0.42	0.38
Fit intercept	0.0057	0.0066
Correlation Coefficient	0.56	0.56
Mean bias	-0.0061	-0.0060
Mean relative bias	-28 %	-28%
Bias Standard deviation	0.0048	0.0049
Mean difference uncertainty	0.0038	0.0038

Figure 3.3.4.21 and Figure 3.3.4.22 show the measurements distribution of SPIRE and CYGNSS co-located couples in terms of relative occurrences of a certain measurement result (bin width equal to 0.0025). For both versions, the bias between the two datasets is evident, with SPIRE distribution presenting a more peaked and thinner shape with respect to CYGNSS.

Figure 3.3.4.19: SPIRE V1 vs CYGNSS mss scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.4.20: SPIRE V2 vs CYGNSS mss scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.4.21: SPIRE V1 and CYGNSS co-located measurements histogram.

Figure 3.3.4.22: SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS co-located measurements histogram.

Figure 3.3.4.23 and Figure 3.3.4.24 report the results of the quantile-quantile plot; in the left panel of both figures, each dataset (blue for SPIRE, orange for CYGNSS) has been compared with the gaussian distribution that best fits its measurements, represented by the blue and red lines for SPIRE and CYGNSS datasets respectively. In the y-axis the values of measurements are represented, while the x-axis represents the values of a gaussian distribution expressed in terms of number of standard deviations. The two datasets seem to be well represented by a gaussian distribution; V1 shows a slight deviation in the left tail (low mss values) and a more pronounced deviation in the right tail (high mss), while the left tail deviation of V2 appears to be more pronounced while the right tail appear to be closer to the gauss fit. In both versions, the distributions of SPIRE and CYGNSS appear to be fitted by different gaussians, with different mean value and variance, confirming again the bias between the measurements.

Figure 3.3.4.23: SPIRE V1 vs CYGNSS qq plots; (left) comparison of the two datasets with the gaussian theoretical distribution, (right) comparison of SPIRE and CYGNSS data distribution.

Figure 3.3.4.24: SPIRE V2 vs CYGNSS qq plots; (left) comparison of the two datasets with the gaussian theoretical distribution, (right) comparison of SPIRE and CYGNSS data distribution.

The right panels confirms that the differences are more pronounced for larger value of mss, above 0.03, associated with stronger winds, while below 0.03 the two datasets can be approximated by two different gaussian distributions (straight line with different slope from $y = x$).

Figure 3.3.4.25: SPIRE V1-CYGNSS differences vs CYGNSS measurements.

Figure 3.3.4.25 and Figure 3.3.4.26 show the differences between SPIRE and CYGNSS plotted against CYGNSS measurement results (orange dots) and the mean and standard deviation of this difference (dots and shadow respectively) for V1 and V2. These last two quantities have been calculated dividing the measurements value in bins of 0.0025 of thickness and calculating the statistics of values within each bin. The bias become more and more pronounced for larger values of mss; at 0.0365 is -0.02, becoming even more negative for greater mss values, even if the low number of couples considered in the last

bins should introduce non negligible statistical fluctuations. Both versions display comparable bias averages. The number of couples per bin is reported in Figure 3.3.4.27.

Figure 3.3.4.26: SPIRE V2-CYGNSS differences vs CYGNSS measurements (V1 mean values are reported for comparison).

Figure 3.3.4.27: mss, number of couples per bin (bin width 0.0025).

Figure 3.3.4.28 shows the histogram of the differences between mss SPIRE and CYGNSS (green and blue lines and dots) and the result of a gaussian fit (dashed lines). The histogram bins width is 0.0020; the V1 fit gaussian is centred at -0.0061 with a sigma of 0.0039 while the V2 is centred at -0.0060 with a sigma of 0.0035; these values are indicative of the mean bias and uncertainty characterizing the distribution and are related to the mean bias and standard deviation shown in Table 10, with a good agreement for the mean values and a discrepancy on the standard deviation, probably due to the non-perfect gaussian distribution of the differences.

Analysing the ratio between differences and difference uncertainty, $r = \Delta/\sigma$, we found the larger part of the population not within the measurement uncertainty of CYGNSS. This is shown by Figure 3.3.4.29 and Figure 3.3.4.30, where the histogram of the values of r is plotted. Histogram has been built using 0.25 width bins of r ; the differences within CYGNSS uncertainty are in the right tail of the distribution (green area) and represent 23.3% for V1 and 21.5% for V2 of the total couples. The cyan and purple areas referring to significant negative differences represent the majority of the population with values of 39.8% and 34.7% respectively for V1 and 42.6% and 33.0% for V2, while the yellow and red areas, referring to significant positive differences, are the 1.1% and 0.6% for V1 and 1.2% and 1.3% for V2.

Figure 3.3.4.28: SPIRE-CYGNSS mss difference histogram

Figure 3.3.4.29: histogram of ratio between mss V1 difference and CYGNSS uncertainty. The coloured area is reported in the legend.

Figure 3.3.4.30: histogram of ratio between mss V2 difference and CYGNSS uncertainty. The coloured area is reported in the legend.

Figure 3.3.4.31: study of the ratio between differences and difference uncertainties of V1 as function of CYGNSS measurements.

Figure 3.3.4.32: study of the ratio between differences and uncertainties of V2 as function of CYGNSS measurements (V1 mean values are reported for comparison).

Figure 3.3.4.33: occurrence of significant differences per mss bin.

Figure 3.3.4.31 and Figure 3.3.4.32 show the ratio between r as function of the CYGNSS measurement values (blue dots). The bins in this analysis are 0.0025, the same of those used for Figure 3.3.4.25. The purple curve represents the average of the ratios calculated within a certain measurement bin, with the standard deviation shown by the purple area. The frequency of significant differences is displayed by Figure 3.3.4.33. The larger part of SPIRE mss measurement are not within CYGNSS uncertainty; r means calculated from the 0.005-0.0075 bin to higher mss, have values below -1, further decreasing in the right bins. The standard deviation calculated for the r population of the left bins (low mss values) is higher with respect of the other bins, causing the majority of measurements fall off of the $-1 \leq r \leq 1$ region even if the average r is within it. The oscillations in the right part of the r means series are due probably to the low number of couples in the bins.

3.3.5 SPIRE vs CYGNSS nbrcs comparison

In order to explain the large bias found in the mss comparison we proceed to compare the normalized bistatic radar cross section (nbrcs) measured by CYGNSS and SPIRE. These values are directly related to the mss values from the equation $mss = |R(\theta)|^2 / nbrcs$, in which in the numerator we have the Fresnel complex reflection coefficient and, in the denominator, the nbrcs. The Fresnel coefficient is calculated using ancillary data while nbrcs is measured and reported in the SPIRE Ocean products and also in CYGNSS mss product. No uncertainty is provided for nbrcs for both satellites. Given the small differences between V1 and V2 regarding mss the comparison will be carried on just using V2 dataset.

The number of couples, their spatial and temporal distribution and the measurements screening are the same of those seen for mss V2 dataset co-located with CYGNSS. Co-location criteria are identical to those used for mss: 0.23 deg maximum latitude/longitude distance (about 25 km), and 15 minutes. SPIRE nbrcs is given in dB, while CYGNSS nbrcs is dimensionless, so SPIRE nbrcs will be examined after a process of linearization:

$$nbrcs = 10^{\frac{nbrcs_{dB}}{10}}$$

3.3.5.1 Spatial and temporal analysis

Figure 3.3.5.1 and Figure 3.3.5.2 reports the maps of nbrcs measured by the two satellites averaged during the entire intercomparison period (2 deg latitude, 5 deg longitude grid). Immediately a strong bias emerges between the datasets, even if they recognize similar structures; again, the equator shows stronger nbrcs, associated to more coherent signal reflections due to lower winds, so calm sea and lower values of mss. The absolute and relative spatial difference is shown in Figure 3.3.5.3 and Figure 3.3.5.4. The spatial differences are within [-4.4, 67.2] with mean value of 17.5 and standard deviation equal to 9.5 and the relative differences are within [-11, 121]% with mean value equal to 49% and standard deviation of 21%.

Timeseries of nbrcs are shown in Figure 3.3.5.5; as in the previous case each dot represents the daily average of all measurements collected in the entire intercomparison region. Even here the bias between the two instrument is evident. The time difference is presented in Figure 3.3.5.6. Timeseries differences are within [-4.4, 52.1] with a mean value of 16.8 and a standard deviation of 10.3; relative differences are within [-9, 112]%, with a mean value of 46% and a standard deviation of 25%.

Figure 3.3.5.1: SPIRE V2 nbrcs map.

Figure 3.3.5.2: CYGNSS (co-located V2) nbrcs map.

Figure 3.3.5.3: SPIRE V2 - CYGNSS nbrcs difference map.

Figure 3.3.5.4: SPIRE V2 - CYGNSS nbrcs relative difference map.

Figure 3.3.5.5: daily averages of SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS nbrcs measurements.

Figure 3.3.5.6: SPIRE V2 - CYGNSS nbrcs absolute and relative differences vs time.

3.3.5.2 Statistical analysis

The nbrcs scatterplot is presented in Figure 3.3.5.7, with statistical results and mean bias characteristics reported in Table 11.

Figure 3.3.5.7: SPIRE V2 - CYGNSS nbrcs scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.8 displays the distribution of co-located nbrcs measurements (bin width equal to 4): SPIRE measurements are generally higher (distribution peak at 42) with respect to CYGNSS (distribution peak at 31), on the contrary of what seen for mss (nbrcs is at the denominator in mss calculation). The high correlation coefficient (0.75) found could suggest a discrepancy in the calibration processes of the two instruments, as suggested by [RD-10] Al-Khadi et al. (2023).

Table 11: SPIRE vs CYGNSS nbrcs bias analysis.

nbrcs	SPIRE V2 - CYGNSS
Number of couples	4164
Fit slope	1.57
Fit intercept	-2.00
Correlation Coefficient	0.75
Mean bias	18.76
Mean relative bias	-28%
Bias Standard deviation	21.35

Figure 3.3.5.8: SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS nbrcs co-located measurements histogram.

Figure 3.3.5.9 reports the nbrcs qq-plots. In the left panel the distribution of SPIRE and CYGNSS have been fitted with different gaussians (represented by blue and red lines respectively). Datasets appear to have similar behaviour, diverging from gaussian distribution for high nbrcs; however, the gaussian distributions that best fit the datasets are different. This is confirmed in right panel, on which the quantile-quantile distribution of SPIRE vs CYGNSS is plotted: the quantile relations can be approximated as linear, different from the ideal agreement line. A discrepancy in the calibration could effectively be one of the reasons of this behaviour.

Figure 3.3.5.9: SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS qq-plots; (left) comparison of the two datasets with the gaussian theoretical distribution, (right) comparison of SPIRE and CYGNSS data distribution.

Figure 3.3.5.10 reports the differences as function of the reference measurements (orange dots). Green dots represent the average values of all the differences of each bin (bin width equal to 4) with standard deviation shown by the shaded area. The average differences are equal to 30 for low values of nbrcs, have a relative minimum of 15 for nbrcs values equal to 30 and increase again when nbrcs reaches 60. Greater nbrcs bins are characterized by less measurements density and more disperse difference values, leading an increase of the standard deviation and fluctuations.

The number of co-located couples per bin is reported in Figure 3.3.5.11. The maximum occurrence is at the 28-32 bin.

Figure 3.3.5.10: SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS nbrcs differences vs CYGNSS measurements.

Figure 3.3.5.11: SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS nbrcs number of couples per bin (bin width 4).

Figure 3.3.5.12: SPIRE V2 and CYGNSS nbrcs difference histogram.

Figure 3.3.5.12 reports the differences histogram (bin width equal to 2) and the results of a gaussian fit (dashed line). Gauss fit is centred at 14.5 with a sigma of 8.4. The deviation of the sigma with respect to the standard deviation calculated in Table 11 could be attributed to the average operation that reduces the amplitude of the oscillations seen in

Figure 3.3.5.11 for high values of nbrcs. These values suggest as the larger part of the measurements of SPIRE will be affected by a positive bias with respect to CYGNSS.

3.4 Results Compliance

According to the criteria published in RD-2 we propose for all the described intercomparison exercises, for both wind speed (SPIRE vs CYGNSS, SPIRE vs ASCAT, SPIRE vs TAO) and mss (SPIRE vs CYGNSS) a Validation Method between Good and Excellent.

The Good grade is assigned, citing RD-2, for methodology that “covers a range of satellite measurements that represents typical use cases, using representative reference measurements. Uncertainty information not available for reference data”, while Excellent grade is assigned for methodology that “assesses satellite measurements and reference data with respect to their characterised uncertainties. Reference measurements are assessed to be well representative of the satellite measurements.” In this work we presented an assessment that largely employs the uncertainties given with SPIRE (if available as in case of wind speed) and references datasets as requested by the excellent grade. The second requirement for the excellent grade is the assessment of a dataset well representative of the satellite measurements. The SPIRE datasets analysed is limited to an equatorial region during Summer. The excellent grade should be fully achieved with a larger dataset, covering more latitudes, and extending into the four seasons.

Figure 3.3.5.1: mean values of differences as function of the reference measurements.

According to the criteria published in RD-2 we propose for the wind speed intercomparison exercises a Validation Results grade of Good. SPIRE wind measurements present a good agreement with the references examined for winds below 8 m/s with the larger part of measurements analysed in agreement within the uncertainty. However, a systematic bias emerges affecting winds above 8 m/s with the greater part of the found significant differences focused on this region of the measurement spectrum. This bias can reach values of -2 m/s for winds speed above 10 m/s of the reference (20%) and must be taken into serious consideration in the analysis of energetic phenomena (hurricanes, tornadoes,

etc.). Figure 3.3.5.1 reports the mean differences as function of the reference measurements for all comparison references examined in the study; the standard deviations are indicated by vertical bars; the comparison results agreed. In both comparison V2 mean difference values are slightly larger (see Table 12 for mean differences and standard deviations calculated for the various references), mitigating the effect on the stronger wind at the cost of the introduction of larger systematic error on lower wind measurements. Figure 3.3.5.2 shows the difference between V2 and V1 mean bias as functions of reference wind speed. The outliers in the plots could be caused by statistical oscillations due to the low number of couples for the TAO bins.

Table 12: mean difference and standard deviation between V2 and V1 bias.

V2 – V1 bias difference	Mean [m/s]	Standard deviation [m/s]
CYGNSS	0.22	0.11
ASCAT	0.51	0.40
TAO	0.40	0.39

Figure 3.3.5.2: bias difference per reference Wind Speed.

We propose for the mss intercomparison exercise a Validation Results grade of Basic. The two instruments show some agreement, revealing similar features in the spatial maps (minimum at the equator, southern region characterized by larger mss) and showing a similar trend in the temporal analysis. The statistical analysis shows a correlation of 0.56 and a bias of -0.0061, not within the reference mean uncertainty (0.0038) with no relevant changes in V2 with respect of V1. The possible cause of this strong bias is maybe a different estimation of the normalized bistatic radar cross section, directly involved in the mss calculation, between CYGNSS and SPIRE. Al-Khaldi et al. (2023) [RD-10] found a bias between SPIRE and CYGNSS normalized bistatic radar cross section, with SPIRE measuring larger values (leading to lower mss). Results found for nbracs comparison agreed with those found by the cited paper.

We propose for the nbrcs comparison a Validation Methods grade of Good; in this comparison uncertainty were not available for both SPIRE and reference. We also propose a Validation Results grade of Basic: the two datasets reveal a good correlation (0.74) but are affected by a strong bias maybe due discrepancy in the calibration methods of the two satellites as suggested by Al-Khaldi et al. (2023) [RD-10].

The horizontal resolutions of all the examined products are of the order of hundreds of km², several order of magnitude greater than the geometrical accuracy requested for correct satellites geo-localization; for this reason, we considered the Geometrical Validation outside of the scope of this study, and the spatial parameters and accuracies provided by the data suitable for the type of measurement provided by the mission.

4. TAO INTERCOMPARISON, SINGLE STATION RESULTS

In what follow the results for each ground station will be presented. The number of SPIRE co-located measurements does not allow to apply a statistical significant analysis to the single station for both versions, but we decided to present the obtained results for completeness. We present the plot of time series, the difference as function of time and a scatterplot with the available data. In the time series and difference plots the legend is not present to help readability. Generally, dots and bars represent measurements and uncertainties, SPIRE V1 is in blue, SPIRE V2 in green, CYGNSS in orange, ASCAT in red and TAO in purple. In the scatterplot legend intercept (q), slope (m) and fit correlation coefficient (c) are presents.

Table 13, Table 14, Table 15 and Table 16 report the statistical results of SPIRE, CYGNSS and ASCAT respectively per ground station. The column of the table reports in order: latitude [deg], longitude [deg], number of co-located couples, number of significant differences (larger than the satellite-ground combined uncertainty), the ratio between the number of significant differences and the total couples, the mean and standard deviation of $r = \Delta/\sigma$, in which Δ is the difference satellite-TAO and σ the combined uncertainty, the mean value and standard deviation of σ , the mean value and standard deviation of Δ . Even if SPIRE present a low number of co-located couples, a useful indication given by Table 13 is the very few number of couples presenting significant differences (fourth column). Only three results with difference larger than the uncertainty, on a total of 81 measurements considering the entire buoys array.

Table 13: SPIRE V1 vs TAO statistical results per ground station.

lat	lon	num	num_sd	num/sd	r_mean	r_std	unc_m	unc_s	d_mean	d_std
0	-125	6	0	0.00	-0.67	1.05	1.44	0.38	-0.705	0.904
0	-95	8	0	0.00	-0.60	0.86	1.52	0.33	-0.745	1.120
2	-110	1	0	0.00	0.37	nan	1.43	nan	0.524	nan
2	-125	7	0	0.00	-0.95	0.70	1.67	0.36	-1.526	1.169
2	-95	8	0	0.00	-0.22	0.56	1.64	0.31	-0.291	1.099
-2	-110	7	1	0.14	-0.14	0.98	1.59	0.30	-0.008	1.820
-2	-125	7	0	0.00	-0.61	0.76	1.60	0.35	-0.929	1.234
-2	-95	4	0	0.00	-0.74	0.41	1.63	0.19	-1.159	0.636
5	-110	5	1	0.20	0.51	0.42	1.62	0.35	0.840	0.713
5	-125	3	0	0.00	-0.25	0.58	1.88	0.31	-0.403	0.942
5	-95	1	0	0.00	-0.32	nan	1.94	nan	-0.621	nan
-5	-110	3	0	0.00	-0.28	0.91	1.52	0.15	-0.334	1.304
-5	-125	6	0	0.00	-0.61	0.73	1.71	0.23	-0.949	1.139
-5	-95	3	0	0.00	-1.10	0.57	1.82	0.18	-1.965	0.975
8	-125	6	1	0.17	-0.37	0.88	1.57	0.31	-0.733	1.405
-8	-110	2	0	0.00	-0.63	0.88	1.69	0.22	-0.958	1.341
-8	-125	4	0	0.00	-0.78	0.21	1.84	0.42	-1.379	0.265

Table 14: SPIRE V2 vs TAO statistical results per ground station.

lat	lon	num	num_sd	num/sd	r_mean	r_std	unc_m	unc_s	d_mean	d_std
0	-125	6	0	0.00	-0.21	0.62	1.60	0.39	-0.168	0.918
0	-95	8	0	0.00	-0.35	0.99	1.55	0.34	-0.379	1.316
2	-110	2	0	0.00	0.03	0.48	1.72	0.41	-0.053	0.816
2	-125	4	0	0.00	-1.11	0.59	1.70	0.54	-1.900	1.096
2	-95	5	0	0.00	0.04	0.63	1.94	0.54	0.206	1.331
-2	-110	7	2	0.29	0.21	0.94	1.67	0.49	0.483	1.473
-2	-125	4	0	0.00	-0.17	0.39	1.64	0.41	-0.368	0.715
-2	-95	8	0	0.00	-0.21	0.65	1.86	0.56	-0.167	1.112
5	-110	8	1	0.12	0.37	0.55	2.23	0.41	0.767	1.142
5	-125	6	0	0.00	-0.06	0.77	1.89	0.30	0.052	1.499
5	-95	2	0	0.00	0.50	0.02	2.44	0.02	1.227	0.032
-5	-110	5	0	0.00	-0.17	0.69	1.90	0.54	-0.217	1.055
-5	-125	9	0	0.00	-0.52	0.60	2.00	0.50	-0.939	0.990
-5	-95	4	1	0.25	-0.01	1.20	2.26	0.60	0.507	2.582
8	-125	6	1	0.17	-0.13	0.70	1.83	0.52	-0.403	1.069
-8	-110	5	0	0.00	-0.39	0.61	2.05	0.41	-0.632	1.044
-8	-125	4	0	0.00	-0.31	0.60	2.21	0.22	-0.660	1.267

Table 15: CYGNSS vs TAO statistical results per ground station

lat	lon	num	num_sd	num/sd	r_mean	r_std	unc_m	unc_s	d_mean	d_std
0	-125	130	32	0.25	0.06	1.22	1.04	0.15	0.070	1.271
0	-95	100	5	0.05	-0.69	1.03	1.02	0.12	-0.692	1.058
2	-110	50	3	0.06	-0.50	0.75	1.02	0.15	-0.497	0.741
2	-125	123	1	0.01	-0.84	0.89	1.05	0.16	-0.848	0.946
2	-95	122	18	0.15	0.10	0.86	1.10	0.22	0.127	0.946
-2	-110	130	24	0.18	0.24	0.98	1.06	0.18	0.257	1.034
-2	-125	115	13	0.11	-0.08	0.90	1.08	0.20	-0.047	0.987
-2	-95	113	10	0.09	-0.50	1.15	1.03	0.17	-0.482	1.246
5	-110	118	23	0.19	0.15	0.92	1.06	0.20	0.195	0.983
5	-125	115	19	0.17	0.03	0.91	1.07	0.18	0.021	0.991
5	-95	50	10	0.20	0.26	1.26	1.16	0.36	0.344	1.390
-5	-110	120	24	0.20	0.28	0.84	1.14	0.30	0.378	0.997
-5	-125	120	7	0.06	-0.24	0.81	1.11	0.19	-0.223	0.922
-5	-95	113	27	0.24	0.40	1.02	1.11	0.19	0.497	1.165
8	-125	71	16	0.23	0.14	1.33	1.05	0.19	0.178	1.401
-8	-110	88	16	0.18	0.35	0.86	1.14	0.18	0.438	0.990
-8	-125	77	12	0.16	0.21	0.77	1.18	0.30	0.305	1.009

Table 16: ASCAT vs TAO statistical results per ground station.

lat	lon	num	num_sd	num/sd	r_mean	r_std	unc_m	unc_s	d_mean	d_std
0	-125	71	6	0.08	-0.18	0.93	1.22	0.11	-0.236	1.154
0	-95	73	4	0.05	-0.37	0.93	1.22	0.08	-0.464	1.155
2	-110	29	0	0.00	-0.44	0.54	1.18	0.02	-0.524	0.645
2	-125	73	0	0.00	-0.69	0.63	1.19	0.06	-0.827	0.748
2	-95	73	8	0.11	0.23	0.55	1.19	0.03	0.266	0.660
-2	-110	75	8	0.11	0.29	0.59	1.23	0.09	0.353	0.776
-2	-125	71	1	0.01	-0.13	0.54	1.21	0.08	-0.167	0.667
-2	-95	73	2	0.03	-0.28	0.67	1.23	0.11	-0.363	0.849
5	-110	69	8	0.12	0.25	0.65	1.18	0.03	0.294	0.777
5	-125	76	7	0.09	0.19	0.70	1.19	0.03	0.234	0.845
5	-95	29	3	0.10	-0.06	0.83	1.21	0.10	-0.084	1.030
-5	-110	76	6	0.08	0.11	0.55	1.21	0.08	0.134	0.673
-5	-125	74	2	0.03	-0.07	0.49	1.20	0.08	-0.092	0.600
-5	-95	77	5	0.06	0.05	0.70	1.21	0.09	0.059	0.843
8	-125	75	6	0.08	0.08	0.79	1.18	0.02	0.096	0.941
-8	-110	75	5	0.07	0.33	0.52	1.20	0.08	0.407	0.666
-8	-125	71	1	0.01	-0.02	0.59	1.23	0.12	-0.028	0.753

Figure 3.3.5.1: [8, -125] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.2: [5, -125] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.3:[5, -110] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.4: [5, -95] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.5: [2, -125] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.6: [2, -110] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.7: [2, -95] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.8: [0, -125] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.9: [0, -95] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.10: [-2, -125] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.11: [-2, -110] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.12: [-2, -95] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.13: [-5, -125] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.14: [-5, -110] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.15: [-5, -95] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.16: [-8, -125] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

Figure 3.3.5.17: [-8, -110] deg buoy results. (top) Measurements, (mid) satellite absolute differences with respect to TAO time series and (bottom) scatterplot.

APPENDIX A Mission Test Dataset

Reference	Product Identifier (L1 and L3A)
TAO	Real-time transmitted data from NDBC Tropical Atmosphere Ocean (TAO) Array, https://tao.ndbc.noaa.gov/tao/data_download/search_map.shtml ,
CYGNSS for wind speed	NOAA CYGNSS Level 2 Science Wind Speed 25-km Product Version 1.2, doi: https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/dataset/CYGNSS NOAA L2_SWSP_25KM_V1.2 .
ASCAT	MetOp-B ASCAT Level 2 25.0km Ocean Surface Wind Vectors in Full Orbit Swath
CYGNSS for mss	CYGNSS Level 2 Science Data Record, Version 3.1, doi: 10.5067/CYGNS-L2X31, https://dx.doi.org/10.5067/CYGNS-L2X31

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